

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE PLACE AND ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FRUIT AND VEGETABLE GROWING INDUSTRY IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15397793>

Abstract

Uzbekistan is one of the most developed countries in agriculture. This article analyzes the possibilities of identifying factors affecting the profitability of farms specializing in the cultivation of fruits and vegetables using economic and statistical analysis.

Keywords: economy, agricultural economics, fruit and vegetable growing, agro-industrial complex.

In our country, the expansion of the area of food crops, the establishment of new intensive gardens, the organization of fruit and vegetable clusters are yielding good results, contributing to the annual increase in the volume of agricultural products, in particular, fruit and vegetable production and exports. As a result, ecologically clean, juicy fruits and vegetables grown in our sunny country are finding their buyers not only in our local markets, but also abroad, and are among the most sought-after products.

At present, the horticulture sector is developing widely in all regions of our republic. In particular, fruits and vegetables grown in Fergana, which has a large school of experience in this regard, are being exported to many foreign countries. According to data, this year, farmers and agricultural enterprises in the region planted crops on 30.5 thousand hectares of land, of which 13.9 thousand hectares are vegetables, 3.9 thousand hectares are melons, 5.4 thousand hectares are potatoes, 4.3 thousand hectares are legumes, and 3 thousand hectares are oilseed crops.

This year, 288 thousand tons of products will be produced by fruit and vegetable enterprises, 120 thousand tons of which are planned to be exported. For this, refrigerated warehouses with a capacity of more than 330 thousand tons, 25 logistics centers, and 90 processing enterprises are operating.

The natural and climatic conditions of Uzbekistan are favorable for the production of a wide range of vegetables and melon crops, which are significantly superior to similar products from other countries in terms of the content and quality of important microelements, such as sugar, fructose, ascorbic acid and a number of other biologically valuable substances that ensure nutritional balance. Agricultural products produced in Uzbekistan, along with their superior taste, are also distinguished by their low cost. For example, in the USA, which is one of the largest producers and importers of agricultural products, the cost of potatoes, carrots, cabbage, melons is on average 5-6 times higher, and tomatoes are almost ten times higher than in Uzbekistan. At the same time, Uzbekistan has a significant additional potential for reducing relative costs by increasing productivity in all major fruit and vegetable crops.

600 types of fruits and vegetables are produced in world agriculture. As we have already mentioned, only

40 types of fruit and vegetable products are grown in our republic, which is determined by climatic features and traditions. It is possible to rationally combine the planting of fruits and vegetables in open and closed areas, properly store them, and provide consumers with them throughout the year. Many fruit and vegetable products are very thermophilic. So, in all regions of our republic there are sufficient conditions in this regard. This primarily concerns tomatoes, bell peppers, eggplants, some green vegetables, as well as fruits such as apples, apricots, figs, and grapes. In order to fully provide the population with them in the required assortment, it is necessary to produce these products in all regions of the country.

The division of fruits and vegetables into different natural and climatic zones is successfully carried out only when there is a sufficient number of varieties and hybrids of fruit and vegetable products necessary for cultivation in specific conditions of the region. As national and world experience shows, specialization, as a form of expression of social division of labor and economic relations, has long been an important direction in the development of agriculture, ensuring more efficient use of land, labor and capital. Dynamically developing economic processes associated with the development of productive forces and the deepening of the social division of labor are characterized by a system of economic indicators and certain criteria, due to the specific characteristics of this area of material production. Many economists dealing with this problem characterize the results of production by the social labor costs spent on their production, and the amount of created consumer values by the costs of living and material labor.

Along with the main criteria characterizing the general goals of the development of the entire economy, there are also private or local criteria that express the economic efficiency of individual branches of material production. In particular, the criterion of efficiency of milk production expresses the features of its functioning as a branch of material production and its ultimate goal. As early as the 40s of the last century, V.S. Nemchinov proposed three maximum principles for assessing the efficiency of the location and specialization of agricultural production:

a) maximum satisfaction of the diverse needs of society for agricultural products;

b) maximum labor productivity with full use of the reserve of agricultural working time at different times of the year;

c) maximum land productivity not only in maintaining, but also in increasing soil fertility.

In economics, it is customary to determine agricultural efficiency at various levels - state, regional and farm. In this case, it is important to ensure a systematic approach, taking into account the specifics of agricultural management. Therefore, one can agree with the point of view of V.A. Svobodina, E.S. Ogloblina that agriculture embodies a complex socio-economic system consisting of technological, economic, social, organizational and ecological structures. Based on this, it is correct to identify single types of efficiency, characterized by appropriate criteria, expressing the specificity of this or that structure. First of all, the entire set of economic indicators that determine the nature of the use of the main factors of production - labor, means of labor and objects of labor, determining the efficiency of agriculture, its location, specialization and concentration, is usually divided into four groups:

- general economic efficiency indicators (product production, production profitability, sales volume, product cost, gross and net income, profit);

- efficiency indicators of labor resources use (gross and commodity output per worker, number of production and management personnel, level of scientific organization of labor, level of mechanization and automation of labor, etc.);

- indicators of the use of fixed assets (fund capacity, investment volume, payback period of investments, fixed asset renewal coefficient, etc.);

- indicators characterizing the efficiency of current material costs (labor inputs).

When assessing the efficiency of agriculture, its localization, specialization and concentration, it is impossible not to take into account the consequences of modern agrarian reforms, which have created unfavorable economic conditions for the activities of agricultural producers. The main ones are the following:

- the imbalance in prices for agricultural products, on the one hand, and for means of production and industrial services, on the other hand, the disruption of more specialized and cooperative large-scale commodity production and the formation of small-scale commodity farming;

- a decrease in investments in agriculture;

- the disruption of production-economic ties, underdevelopment of market and production infrastructure;

- a decrease in the standard of living of the population and a decrease in demand for basic food products, an increase in unemployment, etc.

At the new stage of implementing the next strategy for the development of the agricultural sector in the country, the main goal is to further strengthen food security on the basis of increasing the production potential of agriculture through private production of food resources, efficient use of land and water resources. However, at present, there are a number of factors that

negatively affect the fruit and vegetable sector and its export potential.

Limited land and water resources. In conditions of limited land and water resources and taking into account the constant growth of the population of the republic, traditional methods of agricultural production require new approaches. The rapid development of fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture requires new approaches and mechanisms, a change in the structure of the entire agricultural production, and the introduction of innovative and resource-saving technologies.

The share of fruit and vegetable growing in the structure of agricultural production is more than 32.0%. However, the share of arable land allocated to fruit and vegetable crops does not exceed 20% of the total arable land. Taking into account the objective limitations of land and water resources and the soil quality score, optimizing the location and composition of arable land, selecting agricultural crops for crops that are in demand in the domestic and foreign markets and are productive, will allow us to significantly increase the efficiency of using land and water resources and, on this basis, increase the production volumes of other agricultural crops.

This is evidenced by the results achieved in previous years. For example, in the total agricultural area, potatoes and melons increased from 7% in 1991 to 9.5% (350.6 thousand hectares) in 2016, while the share of technical crops decreased from 41.9% to 34.2% (1.27 million hectares). These figures will be 14.3% and 7.7% in 2023, respectively.

Currently, more than 27% of all irrigated agricultural land is used for growing fruit and vegetable crops. The share of the sector in the total volume of agricultural production is about 40%, and in the export of agricultural products - 43.4%. Along with the optimization of arable land, it is also necessary to work on the accelerated introduction of modern technologies and innovations in the field of fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture, the creation of new intensive gardens and vineyards, the creation of new varieties of vegetable crops that are water-saving, resistant to salt and biological pests.

Weaknesses in the fogging system and seed production. Planting of fruits and vegetables, melons and legumes is carried out mainly in small and scattered areas, where fruits and vegetables and legumes of various types, varieties and forms are produced. All this creates problems in export, not meeting the requirements of foreign buyers in terms of variety, size and appearance. Currently, more than 40 types of vegetables, melons and potatoes, more than 32.5 thousand varieties of fruits and 955 varieties of grapes are grown in Uzbekistan. At the same time, more than 100 tons of various types of vegetable seeds are imported annually. The task of modern seed production is to create environmentally friendly varieties that are able to adapt to adverse conditions. It is necessary to carry out seed production work to create various high-yielding varieties for processing and export of vegetable crops.

The level of processing of fruit and vegetable products. The export of fruit and vegetable products has great potential for growth through deep processing and

increasing production volumes and expanding the assortment, as well as deep processing. The development of the export of the fruit and vegetable industry should be based on the following.

References:

1. Kulikov I. Organizational and economic mechanism of sustainable development of the fruit-berry subcomplex of the APK /I. Kulikov, V. Urusov //APK: Economics, management. - 2008. - No. 8.
2. Sushkov A.A. Organizational and economic mechanism of development of gardening in conditions of import substitution (on the example of the Saratov region) //Dissertation on the application for a scientific degree of candidate of economic sciences. Saratov, 2016.;
3. Abdullaev V.R. Increasing the export potential of the agricultural sector in the context of the liberalization of the economy of Uzbekistan (on the example of cotton fiber exports). Iqt. fan. doc. ... dis. author's ref. - T.: UzBIITI, 2001.
4. Khurramov A.F. Property relations in the transition economy and their features in the agricultural sector. Iqt. fan. doc. ... dis. author's ref. - T.: UzMU, 2005.
5. Murodov Ch. Development of market infrastructure in the context of liberalization of the economy of Uzbekistan (on the example of the agrarian sector). Iqt. fan. doc. ... dis. author's ref. - T.: UzBIITI, 2001.
6. Topildiev S.R. Improving the mechanism for regulating agrarian relations. Author's abstract of the dissertation written for the degree of Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc). -T.: UzMU, 2023.
7. Egamberdiyev F.T. Regional features of the development of agro-industrial production in the context of economic liberalization. Author's ref. dis...doc. econ. nauk. - T.: NUUz, 2003.
8. Umurzakov O.P, Eshmatov S. 2017. The importance of vertical and horizontal integration in the fruit and vegetable value chain. Journal "Finance Directory". №8(68).;
9. Murodov Sh.M. Formation of cooperative relations in the field of sales of fruit and vegetable products: avt. diss...i.f.n. – T., 2020.